

Deliverable D-JRP19-WP1.2

Workpackage WP1.1

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Other contributors	Karin Troell
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1.1. The PARADISE PROJECT

PARADISE (<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-paradise/>) is a multicentre collaborative international project (2020-2022) composed by 15 partners from 12 European countries. PARADISE aims at delivering informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for both parasites. Using NGS technologies (genomics and metagenomics), the project will generate much needed data that will enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis on which improved strain-typing schemes will be developed and rigorously tested. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices will also be developed and tested. Furthermore, PARADISE will engage in multicentre studies to validate the newly developed methods, testing their applicability across the spectrum of relevant matrices in an unprecedented effort at the EU level. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches aimed at controlling FBPs in the European food chain.

1.2 AGENDA of THE Y4 MEETING HELD VIRTUALLY on OCTOBER 26, 2021

- 10.00 Welcome to participants (ISS, Simone)
- 10.10 Tour of the Table and presentation of partners (All)
- 10.20 **Workpackage 2**
- 10.20 Genomics (Task 2.1), [Simone M. Cacciò \(ISS\)](#)
 - State of the art of the Whole Genome Sequencing
- 10.30 Metagenomics (Task 2.2), [Rune C. Stensvold \(SSI\)](#)
 - The metabarcoding platform: progress and challenges
- 10.40 Metagenomics (Task 2.3) , [Frits Franssen \(RIVM\)](#)
 - In silico analyses of metagenomes for parasite detection
- 10.50 General Discussion on WP2 (All)
- 11.00 Break
- 11.10 **Workpackage 3**
- 11.10 Development of MLST schemes (Task 3.2), [Karin Troell \(SVA\)](#)
 - State of the art for the *C. parvum* MLST
- 11.20 Development of MLST schemes (Task 3.2), [Christian Klotz \(RKI\)](#)

- State of the art for the *G. duodenalis* assemblage B MLST
- 11.30 A MLST for *G. duodenalis* assemblage A, [Simone M. Cacciò \(ISS\)](#)
- 11.40 General Discussion on WP3 (All partners)
- 12.00 **Workpackage 4**
- Development of pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategies (Task4.1)
- 12.00 State of the art on nanobodies research, [Christian Klotz \(RKI\)](#)
- 12.10 State of the art on aptamers research, [Marco Lalle \(ISS\)](#)
- Development of post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies
- 12.20 State of the art on capture systems research, [Karin Troell \(SVA\)](#)
- 12.30 General Discussion on WP4 (All)
- 12.50 General discussion, assignment of tasks, AOB (All partners)
- 13.10 Closure of the meeting

Major points discussed at the meeting and action points

The discussion focused on the following main topics:

Genomics and metagenomics studies (WP2)

- The whole genome sequencing effort (ANSES) is essentially complete and comparative studies are now possible. As the necessary bioinformatics analyses require expertise not sufficiently present within the Consortium, external collaborations will be sought (ISS in charge).
- The metagenomics work showed both progress and persisting challenges. Work that resulted in two publications from the Consortium was presented at the meeting (SSI and RIVM/ISS). The experiments on spiked material confirmed problems in the detection of flagellates by the metabarcoding platform (SSI). The material was judged of insufficient quality (degradation) for shotgun NGS experiments, and the involved partner (VRI) will prepare a new panel.

New MLST, SOP and interlaboratory comparison (WP3)

- The schemes are well advanced, and the *in silico* selection has been completed. Laboratory tests verified the amplifiability of the markers and the possibility to obtain clean, interpretable Sanger sequences for *C. parvum* (ISS, SVA) and *G. duodenalis* (RKI). An informative panel of samples has been collected thanks to all partners and will be used for further validation and evaluation of the discriminatory power of the schemes
- SOPs will be prepared by the partners in charge (ISS for *C. parvum*, RKI for *G. duodenalis* assemblage B) and distributed to all partners in spring 2022.
- Interlaboratory comparison will involve all partners, and will be organized in April/May 2022 (BFR in charge)

Research on nanobodies, aptamers and capture systems (WP4)

- Selection of nanobodies against *G. duodenalis* and *C. parvum* (oo)cysts is advancing (RKI). Generation of VHH-cDNA libraries in phage display vector and expression of recombinant phages has been accomplished. Phage display and biopanning test is in progress, and few positive candidate clones against *G. duodenalis* cysts has been selected. Properties of selected nanobodies will continue via immunofluorescence and flow cytometry tests. Biotinylation of nanobodies and attachment to magnetic beads will be performed to run an (oo)cyst capturing assay. Data are expected for spring 2022.
- Selection of aptamers has been completed for *G. duodenalis* (ANSES and ISS) and for *C. parvum* (ANSES) (oo)cysts. Synthesis of conjugated aptamers (either with biotin or FITC) is in progress. Partners in charge (ANSES and ISS) will evaluate aptamer binding to (oo)cyst by several approaches (IFA; ELISA; flow cytometry). Data are expected for spring 2022. The partners in charge (RKI and ANSES) are expecting to run at least a comparative study with the current IMS method and draft a SOP. The possibility to organize a ring trial, as originally planned, might be not feasible due to time constraints.
- The method developed and results from hybridization probes (WP4T2) were presented. The delay in results from WP3 on MLST has forced refocus on what markers to focus the work on. The responsible partners (SVA and RIVM) suggested that the method for *C. parvum* common markers (18S and gp60 genes) should be validated and used in an interlaboratory testing between the two labs. The planned training has, due to travel constraints during the pandemic, not been performed. All partners discussed alternative strategies for method transfer to other partners. The meeting decided to wait for a final method and discuss the matter further at a later stage.

1.3 LIST of PARTICIPANTS

Funded partners

<u>INSTITUTE</u>	<u>NAME and SURNAME</u>	<u>COUNTRY</u>
ANSES	Yannick Blanchard Gregory Karadjan	France
Bfr	Anne Mayer-Scholl Smita Sutrave	Germany
INIAV	Jacinto Gomes	Portugal
ISS	Simone M Cacciò Marco Lalle Paolo Vatta Anna Rosa Sannella Federica Santolamazza Azzurra Santoro Alessandra Ludovisi	Italy
NVI	Rebecca Davidson	Norway
OKI	Judith Olutzer István Kucsera	Hungary
PHA	Ioana Bujila	Sweden
PIWET	Jacek Sroka Weronika Piotrowska	Poland
RIVM	Frits Franssen	the Netherlands
RKI	Christian Klotz	Germany
SSI	Rune Stensvold Pikka Jokelainen	Denmark
SVA	Karin Troell Lauren Davies Anton de Jong Emma Östlund	Sweden
VRI	Iva Slana Bretislav Koudela	Czech Republic
UoS	Martha Benson	United Kingdom

Associate partner

<u>INSTITUTE</u>	<u>NAME and SURNAME</u>	<u>COUNTRY</u>
CRU	Rachel M Chalmers	United Kingdom

